

CURRENT UNDERSTANDING OF THE ETIOLOGY, PATHOGENESIS, DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF CHRONIC NONSPECIFIC CERVICITIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15039794>

Relevance. Currently, cervicitis of nonspecific etiology is one of the urgent problems of modern gynecology due to the extremely high frequency of their occurrence, a tendency to chronic recurrent course, negative effects on reproductive health, and the risk of developing a number of complications. The role of disorders of vaginal microbiocenosis and local immune status in the development of chronic nonspecific cervicitis (HCV) has been convincingly demonstrated.

Replacement of lactobacilli mainly by anaerobic microorganisms (Ureaplasma, Mycoplasma, Gardnerella vaginalis, Prevotella, Peptostreptococcus spp. and Bacteroides spp.), characteristic of bacterial vaginosis, is extremely common in patients with HCV. Of particular importance from the point of view of clarifying the pathophysiological mechanisms of development and the development of new diagnostic and prognostic markers, as well as the personalization of HCV therapy, is the study of cytokine status. Cervicitis and other inflammatory diseases of the lower genital tract are characterized by an increase in the expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines with simultaneous inhibition of the formation of anti-inflammatory cytokines.

Purpose. To develop practical recommendations for women with chronic nonspecific cervicitis

Materials and methods. The comparison group included 30 patients with chronic nonspecific cervicitis who were treated according to the generally accepted treatment method for this pathology. The main group consisted of 67 patients with chronic nonspecific cervicitis who received immunocorrective therapy (Pavisin) and vitamin-metabolic (Vitamin B complex) therapy. For a more accurate study of the complex treatment of chronic nonspecific cervicitis, the patients of the main group were divided into three subgroups.

The first subgroup (n=21) used the combined Vitamin B complex, the second (n=22) underwent immunocorrection with Pavisin, and the third (n=24) used Vitamin B complex and Pavisin.

The first stage of the examination of the patients was a simple colposcopy. Ectopia of the cylindrical epithelium was detected in 26 (38.8%) patients of the main group and 12 (40%) of the comparison group. Violation of the organ architecture in the form of ectropion and/or cicatricial deformity was noted in 4 (6.0%) patients of the main group and 2 (6.6%) of the comparison group. Cervical hypertrophy was diagnosed in 18 (26.9%) patients of the main group and 8 (26.6%) of the comparison group, and cervical hypertrophy in combination with cicatricial deformity was noted in 4 (6.0%) patients of the main group and 2 (6.6%) of the comparison group. The revealed cervical hypertrophy was regarded as a sign of a long-term ongoing chronic inflammatory process. Thus, the presence of ectopia of the cylindrical epithelium and a change in the normal anatomical structure of the cervix are key factors predisposing to the occurrence of chronic inflammatory diseases of the cervix.

Analysis of the results of bacterioscopic examination of cervical secretions indicates that the majority of patients have moderate leukocytosis in their smears, indicating a chronic course of the inflammatory process.

Thus, the study of the species composition of the microflora of the vagina and cervix in women with chronic cervicitis showed that there were no significant differences between the groups of patients with this disease. The persistence of opportunistic pathogenic microorganisms in the cervical canal and vagina in chronic cervicitis can cause activation of local immunopathological processes in patients of both groups.

In the majority of patients, chronic nonspecific cervicitis was characterized by a low-symptomatic course and an erased clinical picture - in 19 (63.3%) patients of the comparison group and 40 (59.7%) of the main group. In patients of both groups with chronic nonspecific cervicitis, regardless of the clinical severity of the inflammatory process, an increase in the percentage of neutrophils was noted in cytograms with a decrease in the number of their lysed forms compared with the control group.

Conclusions. Changes in the quantitative and qualitative composition of the cellular elements of cervical secretions in chronic nonspecific cervicitis in women of reproductive age are associated with the severity of the inflammatory process of the cervical mucosa. The traditional treatment of patients with chronic nonspecific cervicitis does not eliminate pathological disorders of local immunoregulatory mechanisms and is accompanied by an insufficient decrease in the content of pro- and anti-inflammatory elements.

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